

Parameterization of thermodynamic models

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ABSTRACT

Mainly in the field of silicate glasses, the thermodynamic model of Shakhmatkin and Vedishcheva (SVTDM) was successfully applied in previous years [1, 2]. This model considers glasses and melts as an ideal solution formed from salt-like products of equilibrium chemical reactions between the simple chemical entities (oxides, halogenides, chalcogenides...) and from the original (un-reacted) entities. These salt-like products (also called associates, groupings or species) have the same stoichiometry as the crystalline compounds, which exist in the equilibrium phase diagram of the considered system. The model does not use adjustable parameters - only the molar Gibbs energies of pure crystalline compounds and the analytical composition of the system considered are used as input parameters. The minimization of the system's Gibbs energy constrained by the overall system composition has to be performed with respect to the molar amount of each system component to reach the equilibrium system composition [3]. The contemporary databases of thermodynamic properties containing the molar Gibbs energies of various species (like the FACT database [4, 5]) enable the routine construction of the Shakhmatkin and Vedishcheva models for many important multicomponent systems.

On the level of structural groupings (e.g. Q^n units) the glass structure is obtained as “weighted mixture” of structures of system components considered in SVTDM. However, in some cases there is missing the stable crystalline compound corresponding to the particular structural grouping. In this case some hypothetical system component is added to the model and the molar Gibbs energy of this component is obtained by minimizing the sum of squares of deviations between the calculated and experimental glass structure represented by relative amounts of different Q units [2]. However, starting rough estimates of unknown molar Gibbs energies are needed for such regression treatment. The typical example is CaO-SiO₂ system, where the representative of the Q^3 unit, i.e. the calcium disilicate CaO·2SiO₂ (CS2), is not present in the equilibrium phase diagram [6]. On the other hand, the significant abundance of Q^3 unit in CaO-SiO₂ glasses was found by MAS NMR and Raman spectroscopy [7, 8].

Table I. Characteristics of CaO-SiO₂ SVTDM components ($T = 1000$ K).

Component	Abbrev.	Q^n	NBO	$-G_m /$ kJ/mol	$-\Delta_r G_m /$ kJ/mol	$-\Delta_r G_m / \text{NBO} /$ kJ/mol
CaO		-	-	697.08	-	
SiO ₂		Q ⁴	0	981.44	-	
2CaO·SiO ₂	C2S	Q ⁰	4	2502.70	127.10	31.775
3CaO·2SiO ₂	C3S2	2Q ¹	6	4283.40	229.28	38.213
CaO·SiO ₂	CS	Q ²	2	1767.10	88.58	44.290
3CaO·SiO ₂	C3S	Q ⁰	4	3187.40	114.72	28.680
CaO·2SiO₂	CS2	2Q³	2	2761.18	101.22	50.608

We propose a method of estimating of the CS2 molar Gibbs energy based on the linear relationship between the reaction Gibbs energies ($\Delta_r G_m$) of formation of different Q^n units per one non-bridging oxygen (NBO) and the number of bridging oxygen atoms n of particular Q^n unit. In the Table I the SVTDM system components are summarized with their (experimental) molar Gibbs energies together

with the results obtained by the proposed method for CS2. The estimated value gives the calculated Q-distribution close to the experimental one. Moreover no significant improvement can be reached by adjusting the value of $G_m(\text{CS2})$ – the optimized value obtained such way (-2762.20 kJ/mol) is practically identical with the starting estimate (-2761.18 kJ/mol). Comparison of results obtained without CS2, with added CS2 with estimated G_m , and with added CS2 with optimized G_m are summarized in Fig. 1.

It can be concluded that the proposed method gives the G_m estimate of very high quality. Further study of application of the proposed method to other glass forming systems is needed.

Keywords: TD model of Shakhmatkin and Vedishcheva, CaO-SiO₂ glass, molar Gibbs energy

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